

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF THE ORGANIZATION
OF DISTANCE LEARNING

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Annotation: *In the modern world, where the processes of globalization are rapidly developing, which entail the acceleration of the interaction of various systems, cultures, traditions, many countries see their future in political, economic and cultural terms in close connection with the education system. Modern society needs individuals who are able to acquire knowledge and have clear guidelines in the educational continuum. It is necessary that the outcomes of educational systems be expressed in subject formats and have a characteristic of interdisciplinary skills.*

Key words: *transformation, process, individual, distance learning, self-education, information technology.*

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INTRODUCTION

The revision and transformation of the basic goals and attitudes in the final educational results require the inclusion in the basis of educational programs also programs that come from the formation of universal educational competencies. The basis for the development of each individual is the ability to learn, that is, to know the world around and change it in interaction and constructive development with other individuals. The universality of educational actions is defined as a certain component of the individual's actions, which are able to provide his independent ways of acquiring knowledge and skills, including also the very organization of this process.

METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

One of the main priorities of the modern educational paradigm can be considered the ability to quickly adapt to the rapidly changing conditions of the socio-economic development of society. Education is essentially one of the main areas of development of society, and it must be flexible in order to reflect the transformational processes that are taking place within society. Constant monitoring of the education system in the current conditions involves not only taking into account changes, but also anticipating them, which allows the teacher and students to meet the requirements of modernity, thereby being in trend.

Today we are witnessing that there is a noticeable trend of decreasing students' interest in learning languages in traditional ways. Traditional methods and forms of education are no longer able to meet the needs of the educational system and the needs of individuals, which cannot contribute to the motivation for learning activities and the study of language

competencies. Today, in the context of the global COVID-19 pandemic, which began at the 10.5281/zenodo.7222013 end of 2019 and led to a certain slowdown in social processes, the educational system, as an indicator of changes in the social life of people, is forced to adapt to the interests of individuals. And therefore, one of the most popular forms today is distance learning. Specialists in the study of strategic problems in the educational sphere consider distance learning as the most acceptable educational system in the modern world. Many professionals place huge stakes on this education system, as it can save time by making education accessible to many social strata of society.

The use of distance learning or its elements in the framework of the study of foreign languages contributes to the interest of students who are socialized in the information society, thereby awakening their desire to learn foreign languages, including English. Thus, in order to increase the level of accessibility of education for the youth of Uzbekistan, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PP-279 "On the organization of admission to study at state higher educational institutions" dated June 15, 2022, as well as the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the parameters of the state order for admission to study at state higher educational institutions in the 2022/2023 academic year" dated June 15, 2022, according to which it was allowed to introduce distance learning as an alternative form of education from the 2022-2023 academic year, covering 3410 students.

It should be noted that although there is a legislative basis and the requirements of modern realities, nevertheless, the introduction of distance learning into the system of higher education faces difficulties, which include the lack of competence of teachers, the lack of material, technical and information and communication support of educational institutions. There are obvious contradictions between the persistent need to introduce distance learning into education systems and the insufficiency of the conditions that are necessary for the implementation of this activity in the field of education. Distance learning as a phenomenon of social reality has arisen and is developing quite actively on the scale of the modern world educational system. UNESCO defines distance education as one of its most important educational programs, such as "Education for All", as well as "Education for Life" and "Education without Borders". The further development of distance learning is one of the priority tasks that are reflected in the Maastricht Treaty, which is the fundamental agreement concluded between the EU countries.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distance learning is based on new approaches, using the experience that has been accumulated earlier in the field of distance learning. In distance learning, new types and forms of information and communication technologies are effectively applied. In turn, these technologies, which must be skillfully combined with the theory and practice of teaching, should contribute to the formation of a knowledge environment. Based on the definition of I.V. Robert, distance learning is considered to be pedagogical activity, within the framework of the interaction of which the relationship between teachers and trainees is determined, as well as the presence of interactive sources of information resources that reflect all the necessary elements of the educational process, which should include the goal, content, organizational forms and methods, educational institutions, etc. This learning system includes information

and communication technologies that imply an immediate connection between the user and teaching aids, computer visualization of educational resources, archiving of a large amount of information transfer and processing, an automatic system for calculating, information retrieval, processing the results of the educational process, automation of information processes as an effective training in methods, organizational management, training and control within the framework of this training format. Researcher A.A. Andreev presents distance learning as a form of the educational process, where the relationship between the teacher and the student occurs at a distance through various types of communication. This type of mediated communication is presented as a two-way form of information exchange, which is expressed through texts, audio and video formats, various tables, diagrams, images, etc.

The distance form of education consists of the following components, which include the purpose of the educational process and training, curricula, areas of education, education methodology. And it is clear that the classes themselves are held in a remote format. Distance learning is implemented through information technology or other means of information transfer, which include television, postal or other communications.

In general, the use of methods directly depends on the technical means by which information is exchanged. In the studies of E.S. Ibyshv, distance learning is presented as a process of interaction between a student and a teacher in a remote format, at the same time, this form of learning reflects all the elements of the educational process, to which he refers the methods and goals of learning, forms of organization, learning tools that are carried out through specific means of telecommunications, thereby ensuring the interactive nature of the learning process. The distance form of education is essentially more focused on an independent form of education, which is carried out through information technology. Distance learning is closely related to certain educational training infrastructures, including studios from where television broadcasts are conducted, computer networks, educational and methodological centers that provide advice, develop and distribute relevant methodological literature. The distance form of education also implies educational institutions that provide this form of service, but does not correlate with the students themselves. From the point of view of the educational process, distance learning refers to the methods of delivering educational materials and interactions between a teacher and a student within the framework of distance education.

CONCLUSION

From the point of view of teaching, the distance form is a deepening of the student's independent work in any form of education that uses a variety of self-education systems. Distance learning contributes to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities through training and information, including a variety of technologies and various forms of distance education. Many researchers agree that distance learning, a specially organized process of interaction between a teacher and a ultimate student, pursues as its goal the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities, the formation of a worldview, the development of intellectual abilities and potential of students, the formation and development of self-education abilities, which are based on educational goals. Other researchers present distance learning as a kind of orderly process of interaction between a teacher and students, which is aimed at achieving certain goals, or as a cognitive process controlled by a teacher. The main key component of

these concepts is primarily the educational process and interaction, in the context of which the distance form of education is a two-way activity.

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